

INFINITICS: EVERYTHING'S RELATIVE IN THE EXISTENCE AND TRUE NATURE OF 'UNDEFINED'

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ABSTRACT. Undefined being a more mysterious than 'Infinity', In 2024, Infinitics [1] has given enough explanation on structures of Infinities and Infinitesimal but failed to explain "undefined" in Infinitics's terms. This paper will cover the types of 'undefined' and it's nature with calculations in detail. This gives a boarder accept of 'Fully complete Mathematics' and give similar sense of 'undefined' in the physical world [10],[11],[12],[13],[14].

INTRODUCTION

Attempting to divide by zero generates logical contradictions, rendering those mathematical expressions just as fundamentally flawed as any other falsehood [7]. whereas some say there is no universal answer for $1/0$ and the correct answer depends on what practical problem we are considering [8]. In physics, an "undefined" result or a mathematical singularity often signals a breakdown of the current theoretical model rather than a meaningless concept like the singularities in general relativity [9],[10]. Thus fundamentally, zero lacks a multiplicative inverse; assigning one introduces logical paradoxes—such as equating 1 to 0—which would ultimately compromise the integrity of the entire mathematical structure.

Velocity, Position are some physical quantities which depend on the frame of reference, while length, mass are fundamental invariants. What if they aren't? What if they do depend on a 'complex frame of reference'? In the Infinitics [1], it was proven with a simple logic that the expression ' $1/0$ ' and ' $0/0$ ' are different, where $1/0$ represents 'impossibility' and $0/0$ representing 'Infinite real possible answers'. For example, Newton's Second law, $F = ma$, $m = F/a$; thus, when force and acceleration are zero, i.e. $m=0/0$, thus logically for any mass this holds the statement true. But does this prove 'mass' is relative? In this paper, we will see more logical examples on Invariants and variant's complex frame of reference and discuss "Not Defined" in detail.

DISCUSSION

The first example was: Imagine a particle with speed $0/0$ i.e. the distance is zero and time taken is also zero (that means we are seeing that particle at a single point of time) and if we are seeing at a single point of time, that means the speed of that particle practically could be anything, thus infinite possibility but it can't be all Infinite answers at the same time, but the result to this expression is indeed infinite answers, thus the result to this function is "Undefined".

Another example was: If two points are required to determine the slope of a line but if we are taking two points which are same, for the slope, it will result into $0/0$ expression. By logical speaking, that two points which are the exact same, leads to infinite possible lines passing through that two points and since slope of a line ranges from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$, thus there are infinite answers for slope also.

I previously created a set of hyperreal numbers i.e. named as "Alpha Infinity" (∞_A), which has all possible possibility of answers or infinite answers. **Note that Alpha Infinity is not a Infinite number.** Since these answers are all numbers (finite, infinitesimal and even infinity) which when multiplied with zero, leads to zero. But $1/0$ or $0/0$ leads to Alpha Infinity, so does this mean the following:

$$\left(\frac{0}{0}\right) * 0 = \infty_A * 0 = 0? \quad (1)$$

And

$$\left(\frac{1}{0}\right) * 0 = \infty_A * 0 = 0? \quad (2)$$

Turns out that equation (1) is half true but equation (2) is half true. $\frac{0}{0} * 0$ also the same as $\frac{0}{0}$ so does the following also true?

$$\frac{0}{0} * 0 = \frac{0}{0} = \infty_A? \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{1}{0} * 0 = \frac{0}{0} = \infty_A? \quad (4)$$

From expression (1) and (3), we can conclude that only one of them is true and same for expression (2) and (4). The solution for this lies in the book, *Infinitics*, chapter three "Infins and Erne's numbers" and chapter five "Erno's numbers", where I have showed the difference between Erne's and Erno's numbers clearly. Erne's number are non-terminating numbers which are derived from a fraction and there's a hidden remainder (which is a infinitesimal number) and which is not zero, such divisions are "imperfect divisions". When the denominator is again multiplied to such non-terminating, then remainder is to be added in the end. whereas the Erno's numbers are derived from no such fraction and thus no hidden remainder and when multiplied with previous denominator, in the answer such remainder is not added as there are none.

Example suppose there are two numbers which are the same i.e. $0.333\dots$ but one is derived from the fraction $1/3$ and other one is not. so when we multiply both with 3:

$$1/3 = 0.333\dots \ \& \ 0.333\dots * 3 = 0.999\dots + \epsilon = 1$$

$$0.333\dots \ \& \ 0.333\dots * 3 = 0.999\dots$$

Here, epsilon is some infinitesimal number, the main existence of the their difference is the presence of infinitesimal in reality and since it is true, infinitesimal difference does exist in non-standard analysis also (Robinson, 1966). Thus, Erne's numbers and Erno's numbers are the same non-terminating number but the difference is the hidden remainder or whether it is derived from fraction or not.

Here if you see, $1/0$, $2/0$, $3/0, \dots$ or $x/0$ (where 'x' is a non zero hyperreal number), all expressions leaving a hidden remainder behind, although they all leave different remainders, it doesn't matter when the denominator is zero. The question is "But $0/0$ doesn't leave a remainder behind, thus expression leads to a Erno's number and $1/0$, $2/0$, $3/0, \dots$ leads to a Erne's number.

Thus we need to create new alpha infinities, for 0/0 expression, it will lead to ∞_{A1} which is a Erno's number and 1/0, 2/0, 3/0,... all other expressions will lead to ∞_{A2} which is a Erne's number. Thus,

$$\infty_{A2} = \frac{1}{0} = \frac{2}{0} = \dots = \frac{x}{0} \neq \infty_{A1}$$

And

$$\infty_{A1} = \frac{0}{0} \neq \infty_{A2}$$

Some New Axiom regarding Undefined/Alpha Infinity with respect to a function

For $\frac{0}{0}$ expression. $\frac{0}{0}$ can be written as $\frac{1}{0} * 0$ during the calculation but $\frac{0}{0}$ cannot be written as $\frac{0}{0} * 0$ because when write 0/0 as ∞_{A1} in a function's part, we represent infinite possibilities excluding ∞_{A2} possibility such that every possibility times 0 is zero. Proof for $\frac{1}{0} * 0 = \frac{0}{0}$ and with remainder theorem:

$$\frac{1}{0} * 0 = \infty_{A2} * 0 + \infty_{A1}$$

$$\frac{1}{0} * 0 = 0 + \infty_{A1} = \infty_{A1}$$

Note that since ∞_{A2} is a Erne's number we should multiply it with 0 in fraction form (which will lead to 0/0), but since it's in $\frac{p}{q} * q$ and we are using it's remainder too, which is ∞_{A1} for 1/0 expression. In the end, answer is still ∞_{A1} only. so we cannot write 0 as 0*0 in the numerator or another reason could be:

∞_{A1} containing 'impossibility' possibility too? Just like a empty set which, if can, will have only have positive real numbers . Now to find the probability of this set having a negative real numbers or any real number shows an 'impossibility' factor as we have restricted it with a condition that if it can, will only have positive numbers and also the expression for the probability is $\frac{0}{0}$. **Note: the Proof for $\frac{1}{\frac{1}{0}} = 0$ in given in the 'End of the Number line' section.**

$$\frac{0}{0} = \infty_{A1}$$

$$\frac{0}{0} = \frac{1}{0} * 0$$

$$\frac{0}{0} = \frac{1}{0} * \frac{1}{\frac{1}{0}}$$

$$\frac{0}{0} = \frac{1}{\frac{0}{0}}$$

$$\frac{0}{0} = \frac{1}{\infty_{A1}} = \infty_{A1} + \infty_{A2}$$

Since, ∞_{A1} contains '0' possibility too, leading to 1/0 expression. This ∞_{A1} having a content of ∞_{A2} shows logic in practical applications. So in the function,

$$\infty_{A1} * 0 = 0 \text{ or } \& \infty_{A2}$$

And if 0 written as 0*0 in the denominator, for 0 by 0 as $\frac{0}{0} * \frac{1}{0}$ results to ∞_{A1} and ∞_{A2} simultaneously and if the function $\frac{0}{0}$ can't be 'zero' possibility then it's ∞_{A2} otherwise if ∞_{A1} containing 'impossibility' factor then the answer (∞_{A1}) itself contains the ' ∞_{A2} ' factor. Thus, 0 also can't be written as $0 = 0 * \infty_{A1} =$

$0 * \frac{0}{0} = \frac{0*0}{0} = \frac{0}{0}$ as $0/0$ represents infinite answers and impossibility thus from single answer we can't derive to a expression leading infinite answers, otherwise we have to specify for some function that this $0/0$ give 0 only.

For $\frac{1}{0} = \frac{2}{0} = \dots = \frac{x}{0}$ expression. The form for a function like $\frac{1}{0}$ represents impossibility for that idea/calculation/theory... so when we multiply 0 to this, then there's no such idea/calculation/theory... now but the idea/calculation which represents $\frac{0}{0}$ so the answer/idea could be anything (∞_{A1}).

END OF THE NUMBER LINE

It's been said that "there's no end of the number line or specifically of the hyperreal number line" and it's true, but the idea of " $\frac{1}{0}$ " (Undefined) suggests it could be the end of it hypothetically just like a imaginary line. For example, see Figure 1, when we inverse the values of each number and place it exactly at same place, as expected the end of first line is undefined and end of the second line should be zero as after infinitesimals zero comes. But does it mean inverse of undefined ($\frac{1}{0}$) is zero? And center of the second line should be undefined ($\frac{1}{0}$)?

FIGURE 1. Idea of inverting a hyperreal number line

Turns out "YES" the inverse of $\frac{1}{0}$ or $\frac{2}{0}$ or... is in fact 0 and vice versa. According to the Axioms mentioned earlier about undefined that $\infty_{A1} * 0 = 0$ and $\infty_{A2} * 0 = \infty_{A1}$, we can prove that it's inverse is zero as follows?:

$$\frac{1}{0} = \frac{1 * 0}{\frac{1*0}{0}} = \frac{0}{0} = \frac{0}{\infty_{A1}} = 0$$

Here there are two mistakes, first we should multiply and divide only non-zero number which leads to 1 and next is in $\frac{0}{\infty_{A1}} = 0$ because ∞_{A1} can also be zero, leading to another Alpha Infinity 1.

The correct proof for this is can be related to a non-zero expression containing Erne's numbers (certain type of Non-terminating) as follows:

$$\frac{3}{2} * 2 = \frac{2}{\frac{2}{3}} = \frac{2}{0.6666...} = 3.000...003000...003000...003...$$

but where's the remainder calculation? In Infinitics [1], we also deal with infinitesimal remainder for Erne's numbers (certain type of Non-terminating). Here 3 is in denominator's denominator and in the form of $\frac{p}{q} * q$ thus changing sign in the

end. Here, answer is subtracted with $\frac{\text{Remainder in denominator's part}}{\text{Quotient of denominator's part}}$. In this way, $\frac{0.000...002}{0.666...666} = \frac{1}{333...333} = 0.000...003000...003000...003....$ and the answer is exactly 3.

Now comparing this with $\frac{1}{0}$ 1/0 in the denominator is a Erno's number:

$$\frac{1}{\frac{1}{0}} = \frac{1}{\infty_{A2}}$$

$$\frac{1}{\frac{1}{0}} = \infty'_{A2} - \frac{1}{\infty_{A2}} = \infty'_{A2} - \infty'_{A2}$$

$$\frac{1}{\frac{1}{0}} = 0$$

Here, with the formula, the two ∞_{A2} will have the same possibilities of answers since it is the exact copy if first changes and second follows the same, thus their subtraction leads to zero in the end otherwise answer would be $\infty_{A1} + \infty_{A2}$ or simply ∞_{A1} . **Note that there is no guarantee that ∞'_{A2} and ∞_{A2} will have same sequence of possilities.** Since, it is '0' in the expression, so the expression could also be $\frac{1}{\frac{1}{x}}$ where x could be any non-zero number. Here we can take out the 1/x to the side and in the end, $0 * (1/x) = 0$. This result is similar according to the calculus where the limit is also 0 and some mathematical frameworks, such as inversive meadows, define the multiplicative inverse of zero to be zero [4],[5],[6].

And we can conclude that for some reference, undefined can be the end of number line. Figure 2 shows the demonstration of it but note that at the end it doesn't represents an another number line starting but representing that all the values are the possible answers. Like in a 2D graph, moving along x-axis and at the absolute end, the value of X coordinate is ∞_{A2} like when X coordinate at 0 has ∞_{A1} value of Y coordinate. As there is no end of a number line, $\frac{1}{0}$ can be treated as the answer of something impossible so like a broken expression it has infinite answers and $\frac{0}{0}$ as the answer of something possible but has infinite answers.

FIGURE 2. Hypothetical end of the hyperreal number line

This hypothetical end also seems to be linked from the graph of $\tan \theta$ as follows where θ leads to every other positive hyperreal number from 0° to $89.999..^\circ$ but at the end at 90° it leads to $\frac{1}{0}$. We shouldn't conclude that because $\tan \theta$ shows the whole number line idea but it's values are similar. Note that with respect to some function ∞_{A2} can have selective values or exactly an 'impossible value' but for this

case the graph is plotted in the Figure 3, for the expression $\frac{1}{0}$. Similarly the value of y in the 'Equation of line', is ∞_{A2} at non-zero 'x' value at 90 degree and ∞_{A1} at $x=0$, satisfying that intercept is every single point on y -axis.

FIGURE 3. Tan θ graph

In the figure 4, one part of this graph started from 0 to infinite Infinities and then end at ∞_{A2} . If we relate this to Infinities (Ratnani, 2024) where we plot infinity on a graph and as infinity doesn't have a end, it could end at ∞_{A2} unit time as shown in figure 4, here x -axis is the unit times. When treat $\frac{0}{0}$ as number line like y -axis, then the difference between these two Infinity's (Beta Infinity and $1+1+1+\dots$) end point at that $\frac{1}{0}$ line is the difference between these two Infinities.

FIGURE 4. Imaginary end of Infinities

There are some Infinities like $f(x) = \tan(x)$ where it reaches Alpha Infinity and again starts from negative Infinity and so on... But if we look at angles 0° to 90° , the function's infinity reaches it's saturation or it's imaginary end at 90° **at a finite unit time**. Such Infinities are different and much bigger than Beta Infinity where all different positive unit times exist for the function's Infinity. Such Infinity could be considered as 'High order Infinities' rather than comparing the sizes which are only a infinity times away according to the **Infinity/Infinitesimal High order theorem** [2]. We can distinguish such high orders which end at a finite unit time or which doesn't like simple $1+1+1+\dots$ Infinity.

Therefore, if the saturation or imaginary end of a Infinity comes at a smaller finite unit time in comparison, then their size is larger and if it

doesn't come at finite unit times for both Infinities, then the difference at $\frac{1}{0}$ unit time line would decide.

Everything's Relative: A Mathematical Formula's Perspective

As Discussed in the beginning, for the example, $F = ma$, $m = F/a$;....., But does this prove 'mass' is relative? No, for a function it's a single value, but imagine a multiple circular universes moving at a different velocities inside each other and so on, where at the centered universe we have earth, where we are measuring a certain velocity.

Now, for the formula $v=d/t$, frame of reference is important and there's no restriction of the observer's location in multiple universes moving at different velocities or if they are stationary and also, we don't know if there are multiple universe after our universe nor formula does. So for given reference- given 'd' and 't' parameter we are restricting it with a frame of reference, but for $d=t=0$, this parameter matches with every frame of reference out there for multiple universe, because $d=1$ and $t=0$ doesn't match with any real universe, as it represents 'impossibility for a physical quantity'. Therefore, for the $d=t=0$, v could literally be any physical value, as said, velocity is 'relative'.

If we take a non-reference quantity, length (L), in the formula, $= v/f$, if we consider $v=f=0$ case; We can imagine another universe behinds ours, where the size of the every atom is some 'x' times bigger. Here, if we take two rods made up of same number of atoms, compare those two rods from outside the two universes, there's a difference. Some non-zero parameters gives the formula a frame of reference, like in the both individual universes, from their perspective, the rod have a fixed size **but these zero parameters breaks down to the infinite or finite or zero frame of references**, giving Infinite answers (∞_{A1}). Just like in mathematics for $0/0$, it's not that there's no answer; it's that there are too many answers for the expression to have any specific meaning.

Just like the coordinates system, two different universes may have two different perspective of 1 cm in the system, which can be observed outside those universe with an another frame of reference, and so on... this limitation is overcome by imagining a fixed convention 1 cm length to avoid confusions. But the problem of different universes with different size of every atom, is also avoidable as it being considered as a convention. But then also according to the general relativity, Such non-reference quantities like length, time, mass, is also relative in the same universe [3].

Simply, fixed constants can also be relative w.r.t. different infinite possible cases of frame of references of universes or **a respective different approach** w.r.t. a formula. For example, $h = E/f$; here E (energy) is a relative quantity [10]. For a non-reference quantity like θ (angle) in the formula of $= \cos^{-1} (W/f d)$, Work being a relative physical quantity changes the whole value, resulting in a different angle. Here, Force being also a non-reference quantity in Non-Inertial frame and being as a relative for the 'Net force' term [10]. Still if, we take the above two universes with different size of atoms, suppose having different energies with size (observed from outside the two universes), then ultimately, force is also a perspective w.r.t. universes. Since, energy is form of mass and force is dependent on mass. Hence, Every single physical quantity is relative with one and another frame of references, where frame of references having different scales of measurement- observed by a

suppose ideal scale.

Zero parameter as per conditions of different scale sizes

As shown in the above Figure 5, as per different example universes with different sizes of any quantity, show a same frame of reference at 0. For non-zero quantity, if the other conditions are same, with every universe's perspective, they all have the same value. **Note that, to prove the difference in the same other conditions, we also have to take any imaginary different scale meeting the same other conditions.**

CONCLUSION

By somewhat Defining the 'Undefined' part of mathematics, completes many gaps in this logical and number system.

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